

Towards a decentralized geospatial web — risks and opportunities for GIScience

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GISRUK 2025

Summary

The application of decentralized web technologies and design principles within GIScience remains underexplored. We examine potential pitfalls and opportunities at their intersection, and propose three pillars for a decentralized geospatial web: Proof-of-Location, Verifiable Geocomputation, and Peer-to-Peer Spatial Data Management. These technologies offer cryptographically robust ways to validate location claims, ensure tamper-resistant geospatial analyses, and empower user-centric data ownership, with potential for wide-ranging impact for individuals, governments and the private sector across many application domains. Although challenges remain, from platform immaturity to reputational stigma, these pillars may pave the way for more resilient, fair, and trustworthy geospatial ecosystems.

KEYWORDS: spatial data infrastructure, location proofs, geoprivacy, verifiable geocomputation, decentralized web

1. Introduction

Geographic Information Science (GIScience) has evolved over the past several decades into a robust field, integrating conceptual, analytical, and technological approaches for collecting, analyzing, and sharing spatial data across domains (Yuan, 2017; Claramunt & Dube, 2023). From foundational concepts to specialized techniques, GIScience has fostered novel social and environmental research and yielded important technological innovations that have permeated through the public and private sector, impacting society from the global to individual scales.

Many technologies have facilitated the evolution of GIScience. The advent of Web 2.0 has been especially impactful, enabling interactive, collaborative web applications (Li et al., 2011). These range from volunteered geographic information (VGI) and public data portals to cloud-based analysis and next-generation location-based services like routing and augmented reality. However, a tendency toward centralizing data and control in order to more effectively monetize human attention has elicited concerns about privacy, ownership, and equity (Zuboff, 2019; Graham, 2022). Partly in response, a third iteration of the web—often termed “Web3”—has emerged. Leveraging technologies including consensus networks, blockchains, smart contracts, asymmetric key cryptography, and peer-to-peer networking, Web3 proponents typically value a more distributed, user-centric internet.

Decentralized computing technologies offer intriguing opportunities for GIScience, but also present risks and potential distractions. Nascent technologies are prone to rapid change, which can undermine reliability and slow adoption by enterprise or institutional stakeholders. Furthermore, the poor reputation of crypto-related technologies, including their association with various forms of misconduct and energy-

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intensiveness, presents further barriers. Yet the possibilities are compelling: location proofs can streamline verification and reduce fraud while enhancing privacy; verifiable geocomputation extends this to enable transparent, trustworthy workflows; and peer-to-peer data management can improve scalability and local data sovereignty. These innovations present a rich design space for the next phase of GIScience’s evolution, and though there has been some previous work (Hojati et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2022), the area is underexplored. Therefore, we examine the foundations of a decentralized geospatial web, illuminating opportunities that may genuinely advance GIScience, as well as some potential pitfalls, as these technologies mature.

2. Decentralized Web Technologies

The decentralized web, sometimes referred to as Web3, is an emerging collection of tools, technologies, networks, and platforms rooted in design principles intended to enhance user dignity, improve system resilience, and embed values directly and irrevocably into system architectures. These principles emphasize user control, open and unblockable access, independent verifiability, strong opt-in privacy schemes, proactive consent, community engagement, reduced trust assumptions, and rigorous incentive alignment, among others (Nakamoto, 2008; Buterin, 2013; Schneider, 2022). Though Web3 systems are not without pitfalls—considered below—they introduce a fundamentally different blueprint for building digital services. Table 1 highlights a few fundamental Web3 technologies.

Table 1: Some core decentralized web technologies.

Consensus network	A decentralized network of nodes that uses a consensus mechanism to reach agreement on database state updates over time
Blockchain	A database managed by a consensus network recording an ordered sequence of transactions describing state updates
Cryptocurrencies / tokens	Digital assets recorded on a blockchain, often used to incentivize and coordinate network activity and management
Smart contract	A computer program recorded on a blockchain, executed in a consensus network’s virtual machine based on blockchain state and external inputs. They contain data and logic, and typically require cryptocurrency for execution
Zero knowledge proof	A cryptographic method for proving a statement’s truth without revealing any additional information (Goldwasser, 1985); verified in a computer, smartphone, server, or smart contract

Advancements in distributed computing, cryptography (e.g., hashing, asymmetric key ciphers), game theory, and data structures underpin these technologies. Together they result from efforts to reconfigure software, hardware, and data architectures to improve system resilience and enhance user rights.

3. Pillars of a Decentralized Geospatial Web

Building on emerging decentralized web technologies, we propose three key pillars to advance GIScience:

1. Proof-of-Location

Protocols for creating and verifying attestations that an event occurred in a specific place at a given time.

2. Verifiable Geocomputation

Geospatial analyses (e.g., point-in-polygon, clustering) performed in smart contracts or

encoded in cryptographic proofs, ensuring that the analysis was performed correctly and without undisclosed alterations.

3. Peer-to-peer Spatial Data Storage & Management

Distributed systems for storing, indexing, and retrieving geospatial data across a peer-to-peer network without centralized infrastructure. These systems commonly use cryptographic techniques (i.e., hashes, proofs), content-based addressing, and economic incentives to ensure data integrity, access control, and persistence.

Proof-of-location systems can help improve trust in internet-based applications that rely on accurate spatial data, from supply-chain tracking to location-based social media. Building on robust location proofs, verifiable geocomputation—where core spatial algorithms execute in tamper-resistant environments such as smart contracts or cryptographic proof schemes—enables decentralized, user-centric services that preserve data integrity and privacy. This approach also extends to privacy-preserving machine learning, allowing users to verify computations without exposing sensitive geoinformation. Meanwhile, decentralized spatial data management reshapes how large-scale datasets are stored, accessed, and monetized, employing sharded networks, content-addressable storage (CIDs), and local-first resilience. Tokenized data markets, though still nascent, offer pathways for data owners to license specialized geospatial content. Although much of this technology remains in flux, these innovations may help solve longstanding GIScience challenges at every stage in the geospatial data lifecycle, including data capture, storage, analysis, and visualization, as well as enhance reproducibility and collaboration. The example of proof-of-location (PoL) is further described to highlight high-potential opportunity for GIScience.

4. The Example of Proof-of-Location

Broadly, Proof-of-Location (PoL) systems gather, integrate, and verify digital evidence to support claims about where and when an event occurred. These claims center on core spatial-temporal attributes—such as position and timestamp—and are strengthened by corroborative data from diverse sources (e.g., media, sensors, network nodes, social attestations). Cryptographic protocols involving hashing, digital signatures, or other methods help ensure data integrity and authenticate each proof’s source, thereby establishing a foundation of trust in geospatial assertions. Figure 1 illustrates a generalized location proof creation and verification workflow.

Figure 1: A generalized location proof scheme.

The measurement and reporting of location inherently introduces uncertainty; increasing the amount, strength, and diversity of associated evidence improves a proof’s level on a “certainty spectrum” (Jowett, 2020). Verifiers determine for themselves what constitutes an acceptable level of supporting evidence, with more sensitive use cases requiring stricter thresholds. Table 2 outlines several PoL approaches.

Table 2 Approaches to proof-of-location.

Category	Description	Examples
Near-field Machine	Devices validate each other's presence via short-range communication	RFID, NFC, Bluetooth
Network Machine	Distributed nodes triangulate and sign confirmations	Time of Flight, Time Difference of Arrival
Sensor Data	Devices detect local signals (radio frequency, optical, inertial, acoustic); location is extracted or inferred from analysis of this evidence	Magnetometer-based localization, image/audio analysis (Shingleton, 2024)
Social	Peers confirm or challenge each other's presence	Social confirmations
Authority-based	Authorized individuals attest to the location of a person, thing or event	Ticket checkers, event hosts, government officials, surveyors

The sharing and use of location information online is ubiquitous. Therefore, enhancing confidence in location claims carries economic and strategic significance. More accurately proving, as opposed to blindly trusting or accepting unverified information regarding the time and place of events, has value in wide-ranging domains such as climate monitoring, defense and security, insurance, transport and logistics, compliance, social networking, citizen science, advertising, gaming, and more. Furthermore, the reliability of location information becomes even more significant as AI agents become a new source generating and consuming it.

Developing credible, usable PoL systems is challenging, though prior work (Foamspace, 2018; Zafar, 2020) provides a strong foundation. Advances in cryptography and geospatial AI continue to increase the viability of practical PoL technology. Notably, while blockchains, smart contracts, and peer-to-peer data systems offer benefits to PoL systems, they are not required—location proofs can be generated on smartphones, IoT devices, or other connected sensors, and verified on consumer computers or centralized servers. More work is needed to develop location proof schemes that are secure and robust enough to underpin economically valuable interactions at scale.

5. A Path Forward

Nascent Web3 technologies continue to draw valid criticism. Energy-intensive consensus mechanisms like proof-of-work remain in use; illicit or unscrupulous actors leverage open-access, pseudonymous systems; efforts to empower stakeholders fall short (Chainalysis, 2025; Zook, 2023). Though more resource-efficient approaches—such as proof-of-stake—are increasingly common, safety measures are maturing, and proponents are learning from mistakes, caution remains warranted. Immature platforms and the poor reputation of crypto-related services can raise technical and perception-based impediments to adoption, demanding a pragmatic roadmap for researchers and practitioners.

At the same time, real-world experiments with location proofs, verifiable geocomputation, and decentralized data infrastructures hold potential for genuine innovation. For instance, robust proof-of-location protocols can reduce fraud and enable privacy-preserving data exchange, and zero-knowledge cryptographic methods have been shown to support verifiable computations without revealing sensitive geoinformation (Erlih, 2022). These innovations do not strictly require blockchains. Developers can adopt only the decentralized components that address their needs while continuing to leverage efficient, scalable cloud-native spatial data infrastructure. That said, additional benefits may be found in further

integrating decentralized technology where appropriate, such as tracking provenance for reproducibility, enabling or restricting AI agent behavior, and more.

Together, location proofs, verifiable geocomputation, and decentralized data management offer a credible pathway to end-to-end geospatial data workflows that safeguard both user privacy and information reliability. Because GIScience bridges computational innovation and physical reality, the thoughtful research and deployment of these trust-conscious geospatial technologies has significant potential to advance digital experiences and human-environment interaction. Though challenges remain, a guardedly optimistic path based on these three pillars merits exploration and holds promise for a fruitful dialogue within the GIScience community.

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